

The Real Size of our Universe

Dr. Bhaboota Ram Chouhan

MSC, PHD Physics, Lecturer physics, GSSS, Takhatgarh, Rajasthan, India

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INTRODUCTION

It is not possible at all to say exactly what the size of our universe is right, but by some experiments, by our own experience, by our imagination and other objects of proof, some thoughts have been expressed by some science ke devices. Our universe can be considered composed of many particles, spaces and many types of electromagnetic waves, light, radiation is universe, Thus, in this universe, the Moon, earth, solar family, stars, galaxy, black hole and billions of trillions can be said to be made up of other types of substances, in the entire universe there is a particle which is very subtle to subtle and its imagination It is not possible for us that they do not follow any physical rules and even if they do, then we have no information about those rules yet. Similarly, in our universe, there are many large black holes like particles present that do not follow any of the physical rules or even do so, so far we do not have any information about those rules; When there is an event in front of us, so I can say very well that there are so many incidents in the universe that one can see, hear or hear from a human Huss is not possible to know, The energy of the entire universe is certain but it changes every moment differently every day. The visible and invisible planets, stars, galaxies, black Hole and many types of particle, time, energy, electricity and magnetic waves, other types of waves and other unknown particles and waves around us, all of which form this composition together with hot or cold particles called Universe., this way our universe can be of two types.

1. Visible Universe :- The part of the universe which is visible to us, such as earth, tree, stars, nature, other objects, sun, sky etc is called visible universe, because we know it, so it is also known as the known universe.

ABSTRACT

The shape of our universe can be similar to a Vacuole in the cell. The universe is called all things between time and space , all planets, stars, galaxies, black hole, light, space between radiation, Atomic particles, dark matter (hot and cold) And dark energy is included. The diameter of the universe varies. And it is not possible to measure it completely, because the size grows or decreases over time. After the end of our universe, the other Universe starts. It is not possible at all to say exactly what the size of our universe is right, but by some experiments, by our own experience, by our imagination and other objects of proof, some thoughts have been expressed by some science. Our universe can be considered composed of many particles, spaces and many types of electromagnetic waves, light, radiation is universe., how big is the size of our universe that it is not possible for human beings to detect or measure it, but can only be imagined, the reason is that for measuring the size of the universe, there is no intelligence available to animals like humans. It appears that even in the universe there existed a developed civilization, such fantasies which can actually be in the universe. ,Our universe can also be a type of structure of a solid, in which atoms can have electron protons neutrons, nucleus type, galaxy, stars and planet, satellites, other particles etc

Keywords: Vacuole, The universe, dark matter, humans, structure

2. Invisible universe :- The part of the universe which we do not see, which is the part which we do not yet know, or which is not possible to be seen by human devices, is an invisible universe, it is also called an unknown universe.

The size of our universe can be as follows. This is only possibility and my hypothesis.

1. Infinite or finite universe.
2. With or without boundary wall universe.
3. Positive or negative curvature universe.
4. Open or closed universe
5. Flat or spherical universe.
6. Cube and cuboids universe
7. Visible or invisible universe.
8. Definite or Indefinite universe
9. Cylindrical or spherical universe
10. Cone shape or trident size universe .
11. Oval or dumb shape universe
12. Hard or flexible universe

How big is the size of our universe that it is not possible for human beings to detect or measure them, but only their imagination can be made, the reason is that for measuring the size of the universe, Not available, how big is the size of our universe that it is not possible for human beings to detect or measure it, but can only be imagined, the reason is that for measuring the size of the universe, there is no intelligence available to animals like humans. It appears that even in the universe there existed a developed civilization, such fantasies which can actually be in the universe, which according to me is as follows. The universe that we are seeing is not even 0.000001% of the total universe, right

now, the universe is huge; its end is but yet far from human fantasies.

1. The size and volume of the universe varies every moment and its total energy changes continuously from one form to another in time.
2. If the size of our universe is an oval, then its end is also there, and its size type can also be measured, but it is possible when we have such a device that reached the end of the end where it is, if If we do not reach our machine, then measuring it is not possible for human beings.
3. In fact, the size of the universe can be considered as a cell, thus the theory of a cellular shape of the universe appears, there are several factors that resemble equality in one cell earth, atom, solar system and universe etc.

4. The origins of our universe in nuclear fragmentation have been like series reactions, our universe is also composed of so many elements in which water, air, fire sky, time, light, radiation and air etc.
5. The main reason that the size of the universe is not measured by human is the time because humans have not been fully conquered over time, while humans are fully tied with time

By which elements is made our universe ,we do not know and cannot be tell all true about universe material , but our experience ,hypothesis and by experiment we can say that these materials are four types , 1.Dark Energy 2. Dark matter (This is two types) (A) Cold dark matter (B) Hot dark matter 3. Visible Matter 4. Other matter

METHOD:

The shape of our universe can be similar to a Vacuole in the cell. Our universe can also be a type of structure of a solid, in which atoms can have electron protons neutrons, nucleus type, galaxy, stars and planet, satellites, other particles etc. There is also a center of our vast universe where every time the reaction is run like nuclear fission and nuclear fusions, this center can be considered as a big black hole in which new galaxies, stars, planets, satellites, every time make and destroy. There can be many types of cosmos present in our universe, and which can be found in the types of many cells in which every moment is exchanged for various types of matter and electromagnetic fields, waves etc. The structure of our universe can be like a cell; In my knowledge, the size of the universe can be in the form of oval and cell because all the substances present in it are galaxies, black holes, solar system, earth, nucleus of the moon cell, blank space, cell walls, mitochondria types that change their position over time.

Table: - Similarity between solar system, the cell, the earth, atom and our universe.

S.N.	Property	The Universe	Solar system	The Cell	Atom	The Earth
1	Boundary	From where the second universe starts	As far as the sun's light reaches	Cell Wall	The last orbit in which the electron swirls	Surface of Earth
2	Center	Center of Universe	Sun's place	Nucleus	Location of the nucleus	Center of the earth where the metal is in the alloy state
3	Blank Space	Black Hole	Blank part in the solar system	Cell space	Nuclear space	As BERMUDA location

4	The Division	The division of the universe that keeps happening every moment	Unknown event	Cell division	Nuclear fission	Moon made by earth
5	Solid Matter	Star	Planet	Mitochondria	Electron	Continent
6	Matter	Dark matter	Sun light	Protoplasm	Atomic matter	Water
7	Make Up	Space	Galaxy	Tissue	Ion	Solar system
8	Life	Alien	Creature	Chromosomes	Weightless particle	Fossil
9	Waves	Unknown waves	Light waves	Cell waves	Electromagnetic waves	Geomagnetic waves

RESULT AND CONCLUSION:

Some important results of the real size of our universe may be in size of universe as cell theory, because there is some region that's may be as below here.

1. Just as different cells form tissues together, different atoms together form the Molecule, in the same way different solar systems together form our universe.
2. As the atom is found in the atomic mass, the cell contents is found in the same way, the dark matter is found in the universe.
3. Just as chromosomes are found in the cell, weightless particles are found in atoms in the same way in solar families, they are found live on earth, in the same way the soul is found in the universe.
4. Just as the cell wall in the cell, the atomic edges formed by the rotation of the orbit of the orbit of the orbit of the orbit in the atom, in the solar system, until the sun's light reaches the corner, so there is also a border of the universe from where the second The universe begins.
5. Just as there is a center in the cell, there is the Sun in the solar system, so in the same way there is also some center of the universe that is still unknown.
6. The way the atom is fragmented, the cell is divided, so the division of our universe will also happen, whose information has not yet come.
7. Just as the electrons in the atom, the mitochondria in the cell and the planets in the solar system are found, in the same way the stars are found in our universe.

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